

Panjab University

Department of Library & information Science

Assignment

Subject: Information System: Social Science
Information Sources and Systems

Topic: Political Science: Research Trends and
Bio sketch of Political Personalities

M. Lib.I.Sc 2nd Semester

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Recent Research Trends

Harold C. Relyea explained about Emerging trends in contemporary political theory in which he discusses the basic 15 year old conflict between normative political theorists and behavioral political science. The former defended itself as a intellectual tradition of long standing import, the latter challenged as a bearer of new truth, a truth which exposed the traditional effort sat explanation as a sham. In the wake of conflict, the succeeding generation of political scientists, having no particular position to defend, have profited by exposure to various perspective in the dispute. These new practitioners have seen fit not only to draw upon various aspects of both positions within political science, but to appreciate the contribution of other disciplines to political research too. Mathew Charles Wilson discussed about the comparative politics and also illustrates major trends in political science research agenda as in comparative politics. Drawing on the titles and abstracts of every article published in eight major political science journals between 1906 and 2015, the study tracks the frequency of references to specific keywords over time. The analysis corresponds to and

complements extant descriptions of how the field has developed, providing evidence of three 'revolutions' that shaped comparative politics – the divorce of political science from history during its early life years, a behavioral revolution that lasted until the late 1960s, and a second scientific revolution after 1989 characterised by greater empiricism. Understanding the development of the sub discipline, and viewing it through the research published in political science over the last 100 years, provides useful context for teaching future comparatives and encourages scholars to think more broadly about the research traditions to which they are contributing.

- (a) **Empiricism:** Great emphasis is given to knowledge obtained through human senses. All of them look for empirical, positivist, or experience based understanding, so that it can be tested or verified. Knowledge thus acquired is subjected to observation, measurement techniques, and logical consistency. Observation and description precede explanation.

- (b) **Close Relation between Research and theory:** Theory seeks to march side by side with empirical research. Theory suggests to march side by side with empirical research. Theory suggests new gaps and areas, and research confirms or verifies previous findings, and enriches theory.

- (c) **Openness:** A modern political theory feel free to pick up events and phenomena for study from everywhere, even if they belong to different disciplines like sociology, economics, geography etc. all types of persons and groups, various strata, patterns of activity or interrelations, forms of control or influence, psychological motives, etc.
- (d) **Assertion of Autonomy:** The whole community of Political Scientists has begun to assert the autonomy of the subject, and engaged in bringing about coherence, unity, and integrity, mainly through the development of an empirical theory. Easton, Laswell, Dahl all have had been making Herculean efforts to achieve that goal. It can be claimed by now that they have been successful in establishing their all-acceptable identity among other social sciences. It can be assumed that political science is fast coming up as a basic discipline which can give direction and prove useful to other disciplines. As politics is related to control and regulation of society, its originality and predominance emerges automatically.
- (e) **Variety and Heterogeneity:** Theory making efforts by various scholars at different levels and in unconventional areas have contributed to variety and heterogeneity to Political Science. A large number of models, paradigms, approaches, frames of reference, conceptual schemes, perspectives etc., have enriched the field of political studies. Some of them are either too wide and general or too narrow to be hardly

considered more than factual descriptions. However, their ultimate goal is to move towards or contribute to a general theory of politics.

(f) Applied Aspects and Social Relevance: In the early phase of behaviouralism, the goal of Political Scientists was to make out a 'pure science' of politics patterned after natural sciences. They cut off themselves from values, social demands, and problems. With the advent of post-behavioural revolution, they entered the field of applied research, and openly came forward to support societal values. They engaged themselves to find out solutions to emerging crises and problems. Their profession, to a large extent, became socially relevant, as it was in ancient times and recent or modern period.

(g) Methodology and Value Relativism: Contemporary theory-building tends to be objective and value-neutral. Natural Sciences are the main source of this inspiration. A large number of methods, tools and techniques have been borrowed from other physical and social sciences. But it can be said that in due course of time, Political Science would also evolve its own methodology.

Famous Personalities in Political Science

1. Aristotle

Aristotle was an Ancient Greek philosopher and was born in 384 BC, Stagira, Greece and was died in 322 BC, Euboea Island, Greece. Aristotle is called the father of political science because he elaborated on the topics and thinking of the ideal state, slavery, revolution, constitution etc. He said these topics are essential for a man to know his surroundings and environment. He also said a famous quote '**Everyman is a social and political animal**'.

2. Baron de Montesquieu

Montesquieu was born in 1689 in France and died in 1755. At that time France was ruled by an absolute king Louis XIV. Montesquieu was born into a noble family and educated in law. Montesquieu published his greatest work **The Spirit of the Laws** in 1748.

Montesquieu concluded that the best form of government was one in which the legislative, executive and judicial powers were separate and kept each other check to prevent any branch from becoming too powerful. He believed that uniting these powers would to despotism.

3. Karl Heinrich Marx

Karl Heinrich Marx was a German philosopher. He was born on 5 May 1818 and died on 14 March 1883. Karl Marx is best known for his theories that led to the development of **Marxism**. His ideas also served as the basis for **communism**. His books **Das Kapital** and **The Communist Manifesto** formed the basis of Marxism. He was mainly concerned with the battle between the working class and the ownership class and favours communism and socialism over capitalism.

4. Thomas Hobbes

Thomas Hobbes was an English philosopher and was born on 5 April 1588 and died on 4 December 1679. Hobbes is best known for his 1651 book **Leviathan**, in which he expounds an influential formulation of social contract theory. In addition to political philosophy, Hobbes contributed to a diverse array of other fields, including history, jurisprudence, geometry, theology and ethics, as well as philosophy in general. He is considered to be one of the founders of modern political philosophy.

5. Vladimir Lenin

Vladimir Ilyich Ulyanov (22 April 1870 – 21 January 1924) better known as Vladimir Lenin was a communist

revolutionary who helped to arrange the Russian Revolution. He formed the world's first communist state, the Russian Soviet Federative Socialist Republic in 1917. Lenin was heavily influenced by another figure Karl Marx. Lenin basically took the theories of Marx and implemented them in a practical form. Because of this, Marx and Lenin are considered the 'founding fathers' of the communist system.

Conclusion

Political scientists study matters concerning the allocation and transfer of power in decision making, the roles and systems of governance including governments and international organisations, political behaviour and public policies. They measure the success of governance and specific policies by examining many factors, including stability, justice, material wealth and peace.

Reference

<https://www.britannica.com/topic/political-science>